

CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS A COST EFFECTIVE MATERIAL FOR THE 80's.

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The growth of applications for carbon reinforced thermoplastics has progressed rapidly since the materials were first introduced in the early 70's. The area in which they have the most significant advance is in the replacement of metal castings where previously other reinforced thermoplastics have not been considered because of relatively low mechanical performance. The carbon filled polymer grades achieve specific performance competitive with certain metals and precision processability direct to a finished component has introduced tremendous scope for cost savings in volume part production. Additional benefits include dimensional stability enabling tight moulded tolerances to be achieved and held during service over a temperature range, and good friction and wear characteristics.

The technology required for effective use of CFRTP (carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastics) is now becoming established. The materials process very straightforwardly, similar to other reinforced plastics, although careful consideration must be given to component and tool design. An exact copy of a metal part is, more often than not, unsuccessful. Fibre orientation, weld line formation, creep resistance, moisture absorption, etc., all play an important part in determining the overall performance of the CFRP component. The end use service temperature is also an important consideration and is the main influence on the selection of the polymer matrix suitable for the application.

Cost effective engineering applications already exist and several components, including some for automotive use, now look promising in development.

INTRODUCTION

The growth of applications for carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) has proceeded at a rate in excess of 50% per annum since their introduction in 1974. It has been estimated that this year the world consumption of CFRTP will be in excess of 12 tonnes/annum and is expected to rise to 500 tonnes/annum according to conservative estimates, by the mid 1980's. In terms of glass reinforced thermoplastics this volume represents a minute percentage but in terms of tonnage of carbon fibre (CF) it is very significant.

The area in which CFRTP has progressed significantly is in the replacement of aluminium and zinc castings where, due to the complex shape and extensive post machining required on the casting, the injection moulded CFRTP component can compete cost effectively.

Because of the increased mechanical properties of CFRTP over other thermoplastics three highly stressed automotive components have reached the prototype moulding stage. Exhaustive testing of these three components will begin early in 1980. Feasibility studies were carried out on these components to ensure that they are cost effective replacements for the standard production items. Low inertia, precision mouldability and exceptional creep and fatigue resistance were three of the reasons why CFRTP are cost effective in the automotive applications under consideration.

The importance of good component design cannot be overemphasised. Many prototypes fail at initial testing because they are exact copies of the metal components they were intended to replace. CFRTP composites are a new generation of materials and designers must take into consideration many more properties than they would for the metal equivalent. Fibre orientation, weld line formation, creep resistance and moisture absorption all play a vital part in how the CFRTP component will perform in service. The operating temperature a component is subjected to has a dramatic effect on the matrix material and thus the overall composite performance and must not be neglected.

To realise the full potential of CFRTP extensive research work is underway to optimise fibre length, fibre/resin bond and fibre/resin volume ratio. Because of the dependence of mechanical properties on the aspect ratio of the individual fibres, it is important to understand where fibre breakdown takes place so that the breakdown can be eliminated or at least minimised. It has been found that the three major causes of fibre breakdown are the extruder screw during compounding, injection machine screw and mould tool. The effects of screw geometry and mould geometry are therefore being studied in detail.

PRODUCT RANGE

The incorporation of short carbon fibres in thermoplastic polymers has made available a whole new range of engineering materials which can be converted into components by using conventional injection moulding equipment. Carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) do not have the same level of properties as do the continuous carbon fibre composites, but do have levels of performance which in many respects are superior to other thermoplastic moulding compounds and are already competitive with traditional materials (Table 1). The range of moulding compounds containing Courtauld's Grafil carbon fibres are based on polymers which include polyamides, polyethersulphone, polysulphone, polyester, polyphenylene sulphide, polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) and polycarbonate, thus meeting the needs of a large cross section of service conditions. These compounds are supplied as granules and normally contain Grafil type A carbon fibres. Reinforcement levels are normally 20, 30 or 40% by mass although in certain special cases 10% and 50% levels are available. Special hybrid compounds containing mixed fibres eg 15% glass and 15% carbon, or silicone lubricants, are available, and compounds reinforced with type HM or XA carbon fibres have also been manufactured.

Property	Metals					Type A-S carbon fibre composite (1)	Short fibre filled thermoplastics - nylon 66		
	Units	Steel (2)	Al (3)	Mg (3)	Zn		Unfilled	30% glass	30% carbon
Specific gravity	-	7.8	2.8	1.8	6.6	1.5	1.14	1.37	1.28
Tensile strength	MPa	500	200	227	283	1500	81	179	241
Flexural strength	MPa	500	121	103	-	1200	103	262	351
Flexural modulus	GPa	210	69	47	41	110	2.8	9	20
Tensile elongation	%	to 25	8	-	-	1.1	10	3-4	3-4
Tensile stress at 0.2% strain	MPa	420	110	150	-	220	6	20	50
Coeff. of linear thermal expansion	$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{K}$	14	22	25	27	-0.7	81	32	19

(1). Unidirectional continuous carbon fibre 60% volume.

(2). low carbon

(3). die cast alloys

Table 1

Properties of short fibre reinforced thermoplastics compared with those for unidirectional carbon fibre composites and metals.

PROPERTIES

The reason for using plastics in engineering applications also apply to CFRTP i.e. design flexibility, parts consolidation, low tooling and finishing costs. CFRTP also give improved performance compared with other thermoplastics in terms of:- increased tensile/flexural strength, increased modulus, good electrical conductivity and thermal conductivity, reduced thermal expansion, good wear and low friction properties, reduced water absorption, good fatigue and creep resistance. CFRTP also give potential processing benefits, compared with glass filled compounds, during injection moulding of:- reduced wear on screws and barrels, reduced cycle times and reduced component shrinkage.

Ideally these materials should be considered as engineering materials in their own right and not just as alternatives to other plastics or metals. Components moulded in CFRTP have anisotropic properties like other fibre filled plastics and so cannot be directly compared with metals which are generally isotropic. Also, as fibre length and fibre content in CFRTP are low compared with continuous fibre composites, properties are more likely to be matrix dependent. Structural characteristics of components injection moulded in CFRTP are similar in some respects to components moulded in glass fibre reinforced thermoplastics (GFRTP). It is therefore convenient to compare the properties of CFRTP with GFRTP, usually using ASTM data for initial comparison. This data should not be used for engineering design since it relates to a standard specimen moulded under standard conditions whereas in practice properties are affected by component thickness, anisotropy, weld lines, etc.

PROCESSING

Although CFRTP have been successfully processed on plunger type machines, to achieve the optimum properties from the injection moulded component, it is recommended that reciprocating screw type machines are employed. The higher controlled injection velocities and more homogeneous melt that are possible with screw machines are necessary to maximise mechanical performance and dimensional repeatability.

Due to the processing temperature of CFRTP being slightly higher than GRTF it is important that the component shot weight is at least 20% of the barrel capacity. Too large a ratio of component size to barrel size leads to long residence times and possible degradation of the base polymer. Injection pressure for CFRTP should be variable up to 140 MPa. The actual pressure required is dependant upon component shape, size, runner and gate design.

To avoid excessive fibre length breakdown it is important that the minimum screwback speed is used consistent with the time allowable for retraction of the screw. Due to the breakdown of fibre length which occurs when CFRTP are processed, and subsequent reduction in mechanical performance, it is strongly recommended that no regrind is added to virgin compound.

Prototype Development

The production of CFRTP prototypes has always been a major problem. Due to the skin-core effect which is produced in fibre reinforced thermoplastics, machining components from solid blocks or bars of material never realises the full mechanical performance of the injection moulded component. Therefore the only option is to injection mould the component using a prototype mould.

There are three methods for producing prototype moulds relatively quickly:

- (a) Cast epoxy resin.
- (b) Metal spraying of low temperature alloy.
- (c) Machining from 'soft metal', e.g. aluminium, brass or mild steel.

a). Cast epoxy resin moulds

This method is probably the cheapest and quickest of producing a mould tool. A pattern has to be constructed which is similar in shape to the finished component but the dimensions are increased to allow for the shrinkage of the injected thermoplastic on solidification. A suitable split line is chosen on the pattern and epoxy resin, often filled with aluminium powder, is cast around the pattern up to the split line. The process is then repeated around the other half of the pattern. After the epoxy has been cured, runners and gates can be machined along the split line. The two epoxy castings must then be encased in a steel bolster for added strength.

There are two major drawbacks when using this type of mould with CFRTP. The first is that the components shape must be very simple with no thin ribs and generous dimensional tolerances. The second limitation is that relatively low tool temperatures have to be used. Tool temperature depends mainly on the thermoplastic matrix being used, CF/nylon 66 and CF/polyethersulphone require tool temperature in the range of 90° - 150°C. As the thermoplastic melt is injected into the cavity, these temperatures can rise substantially, locally overheating the epoxy and degrading it. The number of prototypes that can accurately be produced is often less than 20 with this system.

b). Metal spray tooling

This method also requires the production of a pattern usually from wood or aluminium with the shrinkage allowance built into the dimensions. An alloy of bismuth and tin is then melted and sprayed onto one half of the pattern which has previously been coated with PVA, a water soluble release agent. The alloy is sprayed to a thickness of about 3mm. The sprayed shell is then removed from the pattern and reinforced by a casting process with more alloy. The procedure is repeated for the other half of the pattern. Like the epoxy mould the two halves of the alloy spray

mould must be encased in steel so that the high injection pressures can be contained.

The limitations of this system are similar to (a) in that components must be simple in shape and tool temperatures must be kept low. Due to deformation of the alloy shell by the injected thermoplastic only a limited number of prototype mouldings can be produced. The possibility of modifying the tool is restricted and usually a complete new pattern and shell have to be made.

c). Soft metal tooling

The third method is the most expensive and time consuming of the three. Basically a tool is produced by conventional machining operations of milling, turning and grinding but by using aluminium, brass or mild steel the metal removal rate can be drastically increased. The advantages of this type of tooling are that highly complex components can be moulded and high tool temperatures are not a problem. This type of tooling can be easily modified, the number of prototypes produced is not restricted, and if necessary the tool could be used for an initial production run. Although this method of tooling is more costly than the other two methods mentioned prototype development is more likely to succeed and progress to the production stage.

Mould Design Considerations

In general normal mould design practices should be applied when using CF RTP(1). However, the development work carried out so far has highlighted two aspects which should be emphasised.

Gating

Gate size used with unreinforced polymers are usually very small so that finishing costs are kept to a minimum or eliminated completely. With CF RTP it must be accepted that as gate sizes are large then finishing costs will be higher than normal. Several gate designs are shown in Fig.1 which have proved effective for CF RTP.

Fig.1A

Film gate gives optimum orientation in 'X' direction for thin components.

Fig.1B

Thick circular components benefit from sprue gate direct into component.

As will be discussed later in this paper, the importance of maintaining the fibre length cannot be over emphasised. Therefore the runner and gate leading to the component should be as large in area and short in length as practicable. All sharp edges in runner and gate should be eliminated where possible. The minimum runner diameter recommended is 8mm and gate depth should be 85% of the wall thickness being fed (Fig.2). The position of the gate will affect the orientation of the fibres within the finished component so that any preferential orientation required will determine gate position. Jetting of nylon is quite a common occurrence if the gate has been wrongly positioned; however if the phenomenon occurs with carbon fibre reinforced nylon the resulting drop in mechanical performance is more dramatic than with the unreinforced polymer. A suitable gate size and position is shown in CF/nylon component in Fig.2B. The use of the over-lap gates will also minimise this problem. (Fig. 2C).

Fig.2A

Fig.2B

Elimination of jetting (fig. 2A) with CF/nylon by altering position of gate to fig. 2B, where uniform flow from gives superior mechanical properties in component.

A 40% CF/Polyethersulphone compound presents very different gating problems due to its high melt viscosity. It has been found experimentally that large flared gates with very generous radii are essential for CF/Polyethersulphone. Fig.3. illustrates the recommended gating for a lever type component in CF/PES.

Fig.2C.

Over-lap gate.

Fig.3.

Large flared gates with generous radii should be employed with CF/PES compounds.

Weld line formation

The second mould design parameter which it is felt requires detailed consideration is the formation of weld lines within a moulded component. Weld lines form an area of weakness when rapidly cooling melt fronts, flow around an object then join together. With CFRTF this area of weakness is more pronounced if the individual fibres do not knit across the weld line. Obviously if there is no fibre flow across the weld line then the area consists of base polymer only, which could be a potential site for failure to occur.

When designing prototype moulds, or components, it is important to ensure that weld lines do not occur in highly stressed or critical areas. This can be achieved by moving the position of the gate, increasing the number of gates or altering the size of the gate. If the formation of a weld line is unavoidable, and in most cases they are, then the flow length from gate to weld line should be kept to a minimum.

Shrinkage

Shrinkage in the moulded component like mechanical performance, is dependent upon fibre orientation within the component. In very thin components where fibre alignment is likely to be high, shrinkage in the direction of predominant fibre alignment will be very low, in the order of 0.3% for a 40% CF/nylon 66. The shrinkage in the two transverse planes will be a function of the fibre to matrix volume ratio.

STRUCTURE

Mechanical performance of a component moulded in CFRTF is influenced by fibre orientation, fibre type, and efficiency of fibre reinforcement. Anisotropy results from predominant directions of fibre orientation within the moulding. This has been seen as a skin/core effect, or a laminate type structure, where fibre orientation varies from layer to layer within the moulding. This was first noticed by simply breaking thin specimens and examining their fracture surfaces. A convenient method of studying fibre orientation is to view thin slices, approximately $30\mu\text{m}$ thick cut from mouldings, on a normal optical microscope where the fibres can be clearly seen.

Fig.4.

Test specimens - Dotted lines indicate sites of creep specimens.

→ indicates melt flow direction.

This skin/core effect is seen in a plaque 203mm dia x 2.5mm thick, moulded using a centre diaphragm gate in 40% CF/nylon 66 (Fig.4). Fibre orientation in the two outer surface skins is predominantly radial, following the direction of melt flow, whereas the fibre orientation in the core is predominantly transverse. Creep specimens cut in 0° radial and 90° transverse directions give 100 second Isochronous tensile creep moduli of 19.8 and 10.2 GPa respectively. These results indicate an anisotropy ratio, radial to transverse, of 1.9 to 1, thus confirming the skin/core effect. In an ASTM type 1 tensile bar, gated at one end, the skin thickness around the bar can be as much as two fifths of the bar thickness, the fibres being aligned predominantly along the bar in this layer, (Fig.5). In a thinner component, 1.4mm thick, the two skins met at the middle, there being very little core layer. Sufficient experience has now been gained to give confidence in the prediction of fibre orientation and design in thin sections but prediction of orientation in thick sections remains more difficult.

- — — — — High orientation transverse to flow direction
- — — — — • Partial orientation in longitudinal flow direction
- • • • • High orientation in longitudinal flow direction.

Fig.5.

Schematic diagram of transverse section through waisted portion of injection moulded ASTM tensile bar 12.7mm wide x 3.2mm thick, gated as in Fig.4.

The efficiency of fibre reinforcement is influenced by both fibre and matrix dependant variables. These can be fibre type, fibre length, fibre surface, fibre volume fraction, coupling agent or size, matrix structure, number of fibres and therefore fibre ends. The most important of these factors are fibre length and fibre content. A programme of work is being actively pursued to optimise these variables for most effective use of the fibres. The aim is to establish the optimum fibre length and fibre content to give properties approaching those of the continuous fibre composites and then to develop the injection moulding process to obtain best advantage of these features in mouldings. It is necessary to establish the minimum or critical length of the fibres for effective reinforcement. Ideally a fibre should be of sufficient length such that it breaks before being pulled out from the matrix when a load is applied to the composite. A certain critical length L_c is necessary for this. There is a different value of L_c for alternative combinations of fibre type, surface properties, etc. The most efficient use of the fibres to give properties approaching those of continuous fibre composites is when the short fibres have lengths in the order of $6 L_c$. The value of L_c can be determined experimentally by making aligned short fibre composites, straining these to failure and subsequently measuring lengths of protruding fibres at the fracture surfaces. For Grafil type A-S fibre in nylon 66 polymer L_c is calculated to be 120mm. A study of the fibre matrix is also to be included in this programme.

PERFORMANCE AND DESIGN DATA

Compared with other plastics and engineering materials CFRTP are still in their infancy. It has thus been more important to gain experience and confidence by moulding and developing components before embarking on a programme of data generation. During this time considerable performance data has been accumulated for CFRTP from component testing, supplemented by certain specimen testing for specific applications design. There has been no design data available to engineers to they have had to resort to the use of ASTM data for 'ball-park' design values. This is not ideal since ASTM data is established under rather artificial conditions for inter-laboratory comparisons of material and does not take account of the visco-elastic nature of thermoplastics, component geometry, or anisotropy. As CFRTP become more widely used there will be a growing need for engineering design data. Steps are now being taken to meet this need.

Creep (Strength & Stiffness)

Like other thermoplastics CFRTP are visco-elastic materials, ie when a component is loaded the resultant strain is a function of the load and time and is also subject to stress relaxation. Thus creep testing is forming a basis for establishing stress/strain data and it is intended that a comprehensive range of creep data will soon become available. Generally the creep properties of CFRTP are superior to other thermoplastics.

As mentioned previously it is convenient to compare the properties of CFRTTP with glass filled thermoplastics. The experimental values of 100 second creep modulus for CF filled nylon 66 are shown compared with published values for glass filled and unfilled nylon 66 in Fig.6. These results are indicative of the level of improvement in performance that can be expected when using CFRTTP instead of GFRTTP. Also the effects of fibre orientation for a single material, in this case a 40% CF/nylon 66, are demonstrated in Fig.7. The upper curve represents a highly aligned ASTM bar (Fig.4) and the lower curves represent the upper and lower limits or 'bounds' of results obtained from the disc moulding previously mentioned (Fig.4).

Fig.6.

Tensile creep modulus vs, temperature: 100 second, 0.2% strain
 Dry nylon 66, carbon fibre filled nylon 66 and glass filled nylon 66.

Fig.7. Tensile creep modulus vs temperature, 100 second, 0.1% strain. 20% carbon fibre filled nylon 66, effect of fibre orientation.

Creep data can be determined by computer modelling techniques thus eliminating extensive and costly testing of specimens. Appropriate input data is required for the fibre and matrix and the fibre length distribution (FLD) from a typical moulded specimen. One problem is that of obtaining a representative FLD. Fibres are extracted from a moulding by using a standard Grafil test method(5) involving chemical digestion of the matrix. A sample of washed fibres is then photographed on an optical microscope. The FLD is determined by measuring and counting at least 250 fibres on the photograph, but this is rather tedious. In searching for a less time consuming method, FLD have successfully been determined using a Quantimet optical image analyser which gave results in reasonable agreement with those from photographs.

Fatigue

Fatigue properties of CFRTP are far superior to other thermoplastics. A typical comparison is shown in Fig.8. Although very little data has yet been obtained from test bars considerable experience has been gained using components. Fig.9 shows a section of a component which has been subjected to a reversing load of 1kN applied at a frequency of 16Hz for 10^7 cycles without any damage to the component. The steel washers through which the load was transmitted suffered wear on the surfaces where the load was applied.

Fig.8.
Dynamic fatigue in flexure, carbon fibre filled nylon 66 and glass fibre filled nylon 66, 50% r.h.

Fig.9.
Fatigue, section of component subject to reversing cycle load F , peak $1kn$, $17Hz$, 10^7 cycles duration.

Impact

Impact, strength, both notched and unnotched, of CFRTP is not as good as glass filled thermoplastics. Like the latter, at ambient temperature notch sensitivity increases with increased fibre content. At low temperatures there is a decrease in notch sensitivity. Both at ambient temperature and low temperature unnotched impact strength increases with fibre content (2).

Shear

Previous work on the examination of stiffness in shear of short glass fibre reinforced thermoplastics (3) indicates that there is very little variation in shear properties with fibre orientation and that an isotropic value of shear modulus can be used for mouldings which are anisotropic in tension and flexure. Generally for GFRTTP the value of shear modulus determined by creep testing in shear is about 0.3 to 0.4 times the upper bound value of tensile creep modulus depending upon matrix and specimen geometry. The same appears to hold true for CFRTTP where the value of shear strength is about 0.3 times the tensile strength depending on matrix. These values have been used with some confidence in component design although shear properties have not yet been determined for CFRTTP by creep testing in shear.

Electrical

CFRTTP are electrically conductive and have good antistatic properties due to low surface resistivity (Fig.10). Polymeric insulators generally have resistivities of 10^4 to 10^{16} ohm and metallic conductors (copper, aluminium) have surface resistivities in the range of 10^{-4} to 10^{-6} ohm (4). Surface resistivity of CFRTTP vary from 10^1 for a 40% fibre loading to 10^3 for a 20% compound thus giving properties comparable with the carbon powder filled plastics but with added benefits of superior mechanical performance. Because of the steeper resistivity vs. carbon powder loading curve there is greater control over electrical resistivity in the CFRTTP compounds.

Fig.10.

Electrical conductivity of carbon filled thermoplastic compounds.

Wear and friction

Mouldings produced from a thermoplastic polymer filled with carbon fibres have much lower coefficients of friction than those produced from the glass filled and unfilled versions of the same base polymer (Table II). The coefficients of friction of CFRTF are lower than those of the base polymer unlike glass fibre filled thermoplastics where very often the friction coefficients are higher. These low friction properties combined with superior thermal conductivity, stiffness, strength, creep and fatigue endurance make CFRTF materials ideal for consideration in applications where low wear and friction performance is required.

The pressure-velocity (PV) limits of a thermoplastic in a bearing application are related to its thermal conductivity and creep resistance. The substitution of glass fibres by carbon fibres in a compound substantially increases the PV limits besides reducing the wear factor of the moulded component. The high wear rates of mating surfaces associated with abrasive glass fibres in GFRTF can be sharply reduced by using CFRTF where the softer carbon fibres contribute their self lubricating properties.

Property	Test Condition	Units	Short fibre filled nylon 66		
			Unfilled	30% glass	30% carbon
Friction coeff.					
- Static	275kPa	-	0.20	0.25	0.16
- Dynamic	275kPa.25/ms	-	0.28	0.31	0.20
Wear factor		$m^3.s/N/m/hr$	1450×10^6	544×10^6	145×10^6
Limiting PV	0.05m/s	MPa. m/s	1.05	4.40	7.36
	0.5m/s	MPa. m/s	0.88	3.50	9.45
	5m/s	MPa. m/s	0.88	2.60	2.80

Table II

Wear and friction properties of unfilled, glass fibre filled and carbon fibre filled nylon 66.

DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

The principles used in the design of components and mould tools for injection moulding of thermoplastics, and particularly short fibre filled thermoplastics, also apply to CFRTF. Attention must be paid to mould split lines, position and size of gates and runners, draft angles, weld lines, changes of section, elimination of sharp corners, holes, etc. As for short glass fibre filled material it is important for the designer to understand and take account of the effects of component thickness and fibre orientation on properties as previously mentioned. Obviously the position and size of gates influences melt flow and therefore fibre orientation. Sprues, gates and runners should be generously dimensioned as mentioned earlier in this paper.

The first consideration when designing the component is to select a material in the product range which has a polymer base to withstand the environmental conditions to be met in service such as temperature, resistance to oils, chemicals etc. The next step is to decide whether to design for strength or stiffness or both. The magnitude and directions of stresses and strains must be ascertained and the component dimensions determined accordingly. The type of loading is important. A continually applied load e.g. in a bolted joint, necessitates using creep data. If the directions of the major stresses and strains are essentially unidirectional and the component thickness maintained relatively thin then upper bound data can be used in the design. If isotropic properties are required then it would be safer to use lower bound data. In any case gating should be arranged where possible for

the maximum stress and stiffness directions to coincide with the melt flow direction.

Parts consolidation can be put to advantageous use in CFRTP. As an example one component which has been developed in CFRTP replaces a steel component and two polyimide polymeric bearing bushes. By using the good wear, low friction properties of CFRTP, all three components were replaced by one moulding in CF filled polyethersulphone.

Since the skin layer of a moulding contributes to or influences the overall performance of the component it is important to attempt to mould-in all features and so eliminate post machining operations which would upset this layer. This is possible because of the ability to mould to close limits without sinkage, even in thick sections. It is preferable not to drill and tap holes for screwed fastening but to mould-in inserts. CFRTP accepts inserts very well. The application of ultrasonics to the insertion of fastenings is being investigated.

APPLICATIONS

The primary features of carbon fibres as a reinforcing material are light-weight, stiffness and strength and it is these characteristics that have promoted the use of CFRP in the areas of application where weight saving is the foremost criterion; for instance in aerospace and sports equipment. However the considerations for industrial and engineering applications differ markedly from those for advanced composites in airframe construction etc. Although saving weight and reducing inertia are important it is frequently a combination of requirements that determines the success and viability of a component for industrial end use.

Carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastics possess a range of properties which when taken individually are impressive but when considered together are virtually unique. This excellent performance/processability combination is opening up application possibilities in areas not previously considered for engineering thermoplastics and cost effective use can be demonstrated even though a direct raw material cost comparison is unfavourable. Kilogram prices are generally much higher than commonly used engineering materials and other reinforced plastics, however it is cost effectiveness rather than absolute cost that ultimately determines the competitiveness and success of carbon composite components.

The end uses developed so far are effective by virtue of improved performance or reduced cost or both and examples of successful production applications have been reported previously (6) (7).

Scope of use is expanding continuously and a number of new applications have entered production with several others at the advanced prototype stage.

Centring Sleeve for Joystick Controller

The good friction and wear performance of carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastics have been put to effective use in a small sleeve bush moulded from nylon 66 containing 30% fibre reinforcement together with PTFE and silicone oil additives. The component replaces a part previously machined from phosphor/bronze alloy. It is required to fit closely onto a steel shaft which moves on three axes as part of a potentiometric positional controller.

Extremely high dimensional accuracy of the moulded bush was specified combined with the need for low frictional characteristics and good wear resistance during its sliding operation against counterface surfaces.

The component is now in service on a joystick for gun directional control manufactured by Penny and Giles Potentiometers Ltd, following successful proving trials when 3.5 million operating cycles were completed.

Automotive Distributor Components

Two small components moulded from nylon 66 containing 40% carbon fibre reinforcement (supplied by LNP Plastics, BV) are in production for use in an automotive distributor manufactured by Robert Bosch GmbH in Germany. Although both mouldings are very small, they are being produced in volume quantities representing the first major automotive production application for carbon reinforced thermoplastics. The CFRTMP material was selected following an extensive test programme carried out by the component manufacturer to evaluate the frictional characteristics and wear performance of a range of materials under the conditions of the application.

Turbocharger Compressor Rotor

Prototype rotors moulded by Courtaulds Ltd, Research Division are being evaluated in the compressor of a diesel engine turbocharger unit. The existing aluminium component has a complex shape and is investment die-cast in a sand mould formed from a wax pattern. The carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic offers the possibility of a lightweight rotor, reducing inertia in operation, and a cheaper component by replacing the complicated and expensive lost wax moulding process with a straightforward and rapid production technique.

The components operate at 70,000 - 100,000 RPM with temperatures ranging from 120°C at the shaft to 130°C at the blade tip. In the 4 inch diameter rotor a tip speed of 1200 ft/sec is reached. Two grades of reinforced thermoplastic moulding compound have been selected for use in the development programme. These are polyphenylene sulphide and polyethersulphone reinforced with 30% carbon fibres, chosen on the basis of their material properties to meet the stresses involved over the operating temperature range.

The results so far show reasonable promise and it is hoped to extend the programme to include rotors for petrol engine turbocharger units.

Gear Selector Fork

The fifth gear selector fork for a five-speed gear box has been prototype moulded in nylon 66 reinforced with 40% carbon fibre. Cost reduction is the main reason for considering reinforced thermoplastics in the component which is currently die-cast from aluminium bronze. The metal part requires machining inside the bore and at the fork tips to meet the operating tolerances. The first prototypes moulded in carbon reinforced nylon 66 achieved the required accuracy and are now being evaluated under test when it is hoped that the good tribological characteristics of the CFRTMP will provide an additional advantage in terms of improved wear resistance and smoother operation. Although this particular selector fork is relatively lightly loaded, the operating conditions are severe (hot oil up to 180°C) demanding exceptionally good dimensional and thermal stability in the materials employed. Nylon 66 is being used for the initial evaluation, however polysulphone offers better all-round performance and preliminary costings based on this polymer look attractive for volume production.

Flat Bed Knitting Machine Slider

The slider block for a flat-bed knitting machine is now in production moulded from carbon reinforced nylon 66. The block, previously made from steel, reciprocates at high speed (up to 1.7m/sec) across the knitting machine carrying a guide arm through which yarn passes for completion of the row of stitches. The moulded component weighs only a quarter of the original metal part and the reduced inertia has enabled the machine to operate at higher speeds leading to increased productivity.

In addition to stiffness and dimensional stability the CFRTP block also requires good wear resistance and a low frictional coefficient against the steel counterface along which it slides. Little or no lubrication is possible because of the risk of contaminating the garment and so a special grade of CF reinforced nylon 66 was selected containing internal lubricants (PTFE and Silicone oil) for smooth long term performance. A further advantage of the CFRTP slider was found to be a reduction in the noise generated at the end of each traverse.

The complex shaped component is moulded in three parts all of which include metal inserts for assembly and for attachment of fittings.

Knitting Machine Presser Foot

The newly developed technique of presser foot knitting is now being applied to flat-bed knitting equipment enabling the production of fully-fashioned garments in one piece and at much higher speeds than previously achieved by conventional processes. The component vital in this technology breakthrough, the presser foot itself, has been the subject of an extensive investigation and evaluation to find suitable materials and methods of construction. It is now manufactured by encapsulating a shaped high tensile steel wire with carbon fibre reinforced nylon 66 in a simple insert moulding operation. This method provides the dimensional stability and accuracy required and the carbon reinforcement provides increased stiffness and improved fatigue resistance compared to other materials investigated.

The moulded item can now be produced at less than a tenth of the cost of the original component construction of tinned steel sheet folded over piano wire.

Components for Yacht Equipment

Two types of sheave pulley are being used successfully in application for yacht equipment. Offshore Instruments Ltd have developed a jamming pulley block which uses two sheaves moulded from carbon fibre reinforced nylon 66 by Courtaulds Engineering Ltd, Kirkspares Dept. The use of two sheaves specially shaped to produce a concave jamming surface greatly reduces the point loading of the rope being gripped, achieving a more efficient jamming action with lower risk of damage or wear to the rope. The design and operation of this type of sheave is made possible by the special characteristics of CFRTP. Precision moulded accuracy and dimensional stability in use allow free running of the sheaves against their spindles, when required, and the good chemical and wear resistance of their moulded surface ensures a long service life in salt water conditions.

CFRTP sheave bushes moulded by Sea-Sure Ltd are in successful production for a mast-head pulley incorporated into products manufactured by Kemp Masts Ltd. Tests carried out as part of a pre-production evaluation showed that the carbon reinforced nylon 66 bushes were capable of sustaining without failure an accidental overload of many times that encountered in normal service. The performance was generally superior to other materials commonly used, eg fabric reinforced phenolic resin.

FUTURE PROSPECTS

The market for carbon fibres as a whole is growing rapidly with increased activity in all areas including aerospace, sports equipment and industrial applications. Historically the small overall size of the carbon fibres market has kept prices relatively high which has been a major limitation of the wider exploitation of the material particularly in the industrial section. Continual improvement in fibre manufacturing technology coupled with the recent increased demand have combined to bring costs down quite significantly with present basic fibre prices only a fifth of those quoted five years ago. Volume linked projections down to £10-12/kg for PAN-based fibres are currently being made at which level many large scale production applications look viable.

On this cost scale CFRTP moulding compounds could be available at £3-5/kg - only a factor of two or three higher than conventional engineering thermoplastics instead of the present order of magnitude difference.

Another major reason for the limited growth rate of application for carbon fibre has been the lack of the necessary technology for converting the fibre rapidly and cheaply to efficient composites. Injection moulding largely overcomes this problem and carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastics seem set therefore to expand their scale of use considerably, provided that continued product improvements and refinements take place and that a solid design base is established. The authors are confident that the current research and development programmes will provide the required data background and that during the 80's, CFRTP will ultimately become established materials for use in high performance engineering applications, enjoying a true volume market.

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